

INFLUENCE OF CARBON FIBER SURFACE TREATMENT ON THE PROPERTIES OF CFRC MATERIALS

S.J.A. Haug, W.M. Mueller and S. Horn

University of Augsburg, Institute of Physics, Experimental Physics II, D-86135 Augsburg, Germany

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ABSTRACT

The influence of two different carbon fiber surface treatments on the fiber-matrix-interaction in and microstructure of carbon fiber reinforced carbon (CFRC) were investigated. The surfaces of these carbon fibers were characterized using x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Carbon fiber reinforced polymer-greenbodies (CFRP) on lab-scale were then produced. These samples were carbonized and their structure investigated on micro- and mesoscale using X-ray computer tomography (CT) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) before and after carbonization. Finally, single fiber push-in tests were performed, in order to identify different micromechanical failure behavior between the differently surface treated carbon fibers in carbonized samples. It is shown that the fiber surface treatment, in combination with the volumetric shrinkage of the matrix material during pyrolysis, has a major effect on the microstructure of the carbonized samples. The single fiber push-in measurements reveals that the different surface treatment lead to severe differences in fiber-matrix bonding strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Surface treatment of carbon fibers is widely used in the production of CFRP to enhance adhesion of fibers and matrix and, consequently, the mechanical performance of the composite [1, 2, 3]. In carbon fiber reinforced carbon materials produced by carbonization of CFRP greenbodies, though, surface treatment of the fibers can lead to brittle failure and poor mechanical properties. This is usually linked to residual stress, arising due to matrix shrinkage during pyrolysis and the hence resulting microstructure in carbonized composites [4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. The influence of fiber matrix adhesion in the greenbody on the failure behavior and the exact mechanism of failure are still under investigation. In the present study, the effects of fiber surface treatment on the microstructure and mechanical properties of CFRC are investigated, in order to shed light on the mechanism involved in the failure behavior of this material. To this end, CFRC minicomposites were produced, employing carbon fibers with different surface treatments.

2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

2.1 Fiber treatment

Commercially available HT-fibers (Sigrafil C30 T050 Epy, SGL group) were subjected to two different surface treatments (further denoted Cf-A- and Cf-B-fibers) prior to sizing. After treatment, the fibers were sized with a commercially available standard epoxy sizing. For XPS-investigation, the sizing was removed utilizing an ultrasonic bath with a butanone solution (also known as methyl-ethyl-ketone, MEK) and a dwell time of 90 min. Then, both sized and desized fibers of type Cf-A and Cf-B were subjected to three different heat treatments, at 180 °C, 550 °C and 900 °C, in order to model the conditions of the pyrolysis process during CFRC-production. Table 1 shows an overview of the resulting 16 types of fiber samples.

Pretreatment	Sizing	Heat treatment	Pretreatment	Sizing	Heat treatment
Cf-A	sized	no treatment 180°C 550°C 900°C	Cf-B	sized	no treatment 180°C 550°C 900°C
	desized	no treatment 180°C 550°C 900°C		desized	no treatment 180°C 550°C 900°C

Table 1: Overview over fiber samples, prepared for XPS-investigation

2.2 Preparation of minicomposites

Fiber tows of 50,000 sized filaments were impregnated with a standard phenolic resin and cured at 170 °C and 20 bar for 25 min. In order to investigate the influence of pressure conditions during the sample production, three different specimen types were produced. The first type was produced under pressure controlled conditions with a press mould of 5 mm width. These samples are further denoted high pressure samples (HP, 0.5 mm sample thickness, Fig.1 (a)). To reduce the production pressure, 1 mm spacers were included into the press mould, resulting in samples denoted in the following as intermediate pressure samples (IP, 0.8 mm sample thickness, Fig.1 (b)). Finally samples were produced, using the 1 mm spacers in combination with a press mould of 8 mm width, resulting in samples denoted in the following as low pressure samples (LP, 0.8mm sample thickness, Fig.1 (c)). All three sample types were pyrolyzed under N₂-atmosphere at 900 °C.

Figure 1: Different sample geometries, a) HP-, b) IP-, c) LP-samples.

3 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

XPS-characterization of the chemical functionality of the differently treated carbon fiber surfaces was conducted employing monochromatic K_α-X-rays from an Al-cathode (1486.6 eV). Elemental composition was evaluated using standard peak-area analysis, described in detail in Ref. 9 and 10.

The minicomposites were examined structurally prior to carbonization on a mesoscale with CT (Nanotom m 180, General Electrics). The porosity of the samples was derived from stacks of two thousand virtual cross sections gained from CT-measurement, representing a volume of close to 16 mm³ of the respective samples. A threshold procedure (Otsu-threshold, [11]) was applied to these image stacks with the freeware program “Image J”, resulting in binary pictures. Porosities were then obtained, analyzing the percentage of voxels below the calculated threshold level (employing the “voxel counter” plug-in, [12]).

To accompany the CT-investigation, real cross sections were prepared with a standard polishing machine (Tegrapol-11, Struers). Since the samples investigated in the current study are all of unidirectional fiber orientation, the area fraction of the optical micrographs, assigned to the fibers, can be used to approximate the fiber volume content (FVC) of the samples. Thus, the same threshold procedure as described above for CT was applied to three micrographs of three different samples of the same type.

Post carbonization investigations on a micro- and nanoscale were conducted by SEM. Polished specimens for the SEM-study were prepared with an Ar⁺-ion-polisher (Cross Section Polisher SM-09010, Jeol).

Single fiber push-in [13, 14] measurements were applied to all samples, which give valuable information about micromechanical properties [15, 16, 17] of fiber reinforced composites. For these measurements, slices of carbonized samples with approximately 2 mm thickness were cut off with a low speed diamond saw (Isomet low speed saw, Buehler) perpendicular to the fiber direction and subsequently lapped and polished utilizing a lapping machine (PM5, Logitech). Push-in test were carried out using a universal nanomechanical testing system (UNAT, Asmec) with a flat-end cone indenter of approximately 4 μm diameter (Fig.2), under displacement controlled loading conditions. The maximal indenter displacement was chosen to be 1500 nm with a displacement speed of 50 nm/s. The push-in measurements were combined with atomic force microscopy (AFM) [18] to investigate the failure mechanism during loading.

To correlate the micromechanical failure behavior observed by single fiber push-in measurements with the failure mechanism of the macroscopic minicomposite, fracture surfaces of both specimens resulting from a three-point bending test were studied with SEM. For both types of samples the part of the fracture surface subjected to tensile stress (lower part of the sample) was examined.

Figure 2: SEM image of the flat-end-cone indenter tip used in the present work.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Spectroscopic investigation

Fig.3 shows XPS-spectra of sized (a) and desized (b) Cf-A and Cf-B fibers before heat treatment. It can be seen that the spectra of sized fibers show no significant differences, independent of surface treatment. An oxygen content of nearly 20 at% is found, while no significant nitrogen content can be detected. Desized Cf-A and Cf-B fibers differ significantly from each other in oxygen and in nitrogen content. Cf-A fibers show a higher functionality, with about 13 at% oxygen- and 3 at% nitrogen content, whereas Cf-B fibers only display oxygen and nitrogen contents of about 8 at% and 1 at%, respectively.

The fibers were then heat treated as described in Table 1 and XPS-spectra were recorded afterwards. The resulting surface element compositions are depicted in Fig.4. The abrupt change in oxygen content as a function of temperature at approximately 400 °C for sized fibers, can be associated with the vaporization of the sizing. This assumption was confirmed by thermogravimetric analysis, which is not part of the present work. In general, the heat treatment leads to a significant

decrease in functionality for both types of fiber, sized and desized. After heat treatment up to 900 °C, no nitrogen signal can be detected, while the oxygen concentration drops to 5 at% and 3 at% for Cf-A and Cf-B, respectively. This applies for both, sized and desized fibers.

Figure 3: XPS-spectra of Cf-A and Cf-B fiber surfaces in the initial state. a) sized fibers, b) desized fibers.

Figure 4: Elemental composition after heat treatment for Cf-A and Cf-B fibers a) sized fibers, b) desized fibers.

The C 1s peak of Cf-A and Cf-B fibers was studied more closely to identify the different oxygen functionalities. Fig.5 shows the spectra of sized Cf-A and Cf-B after heat treatments normalized to their maximum value. Besides the main C-C-bonding peak, located at 284.5 eV both treatments result in peaks at 286.0 eV and 288.6 eV respectively. The peak at the binding energy of 286.0 eV can be associated with C-O-single bonding originating from hydroxyl groups. The peak at 288.6 eV is due to carboxyl groups. Both peaks originate from the epoxy sizing. Besides a slightly higher intensity of the hydroxyl group peak for Cf-A spectra, no significant differences between the fiber surface treatments are observed at room temperature. After heating to 550 °C, a sharp decrease in functionality takes place for both fiber types, associated again with evaporation of the sizing. After heating up to 900 °C no differences between Cf-A and Cf-B fibers are observed.

For desized fibers, Cf-A shows significantly higher concentration of hydroxyl groups than Cf-B (Fig.6) before heat treatment. In addition, Cf-A shows additional intensity at higher binding energies compared to Cf-B, which can be assigned to the presence of carbonyl and carboxyl groups, which are not present for the Cf-B surface. Analogous to the sized fibers, both desized fibers show a substantial loss in functionality after heating to and above 550 °C.

Figure 5: XPS carbon peak of sized fibers after different temperature treatments (initial state, 180°C, 550°C, 900°C). a) Cf-A, b) Cf-B.

Figure 6: XPS carbon peak of desized fibers at different temperature treatments (initial state, 180°C, 550°C, 900°C). a) Cf-A, b) Cf-B.

4.2 Structural investigation of the greenbodies

We now investigate the effect of the observed differences in fiber surface chemical composition on the structure of the minicomposites greenbodies. For this purpose CT-investigations were conducted. Fig.7 shows virtual cross sections obtained from CT scans of the greenbody samples produced with the three different forming procedures described above (HP, IP and LP). Fig.8 (a) shows the porosities extracted from the CT investigation. It can be seen, that the fiber treatment has no significant effect on the porosity and pore structure (Fig. 7), while the forming procedure leads to major differences of both quantities. This agrees well with the fact that the surface of the sized fibers shows no substantial difference in molecular functionality. Fig.8 (b) shows the FVC obtained from the optical microscopic investigation. No influence of the fiber treatment can be detected. In conclusion, the microstructure of the greenbody does not depend on surface treatment of the carbon fiber.

Figure 7: Virtual cross sections of minicomposites in green state, HP sample of type A (a) and B (b), IP sample of type A (c) and B (d), LP samples of type A (e) and B (f).

Figure 8: Porosity gained from CT measurements (a) and fiber volume content gained from optical investigation (b) for different sample types and fiber treatments respectively.

4.3 Structural investigation of carbonized samples

We now want to investigate whether the fiber surface treatment influences the microstructure of the CFRC minicomposites. If an influence is found, it must arise during the carbonization procedure. To study the microstructure after pyrolysis IP samples were chosen. Fig.9 shows virtual cross sections obtained from CT scans. For both samples, prepared with Cf-A and Cf-B respectively, a pore structure on a mesoscopic scale is observed, reminiscent of the pore structure of the green samples. In Cf-B samples the pore size appears larger. In addition a microporosity is found in both samples. For samples with Cf-A fibers, microcracks are observed in the vicinity of mesopores (marked by green arrows in Fig. 9 (a)). The shape of these cracks suggests matrix cracking, with pores as a starting point. In contrast, samples with Cf-B fibers show extended, linear microcracks (marked by red arrows in Fig 9 (b)). SEM-micrographs of these samples (Fig.10 (c)) reveal these microcracks as a sequence of fiber-matrix debondings bridging multiple adjacent filaments.

Figure 9: Virtual cross section through samples with intermediate porosity after carbonisation. a) Sample of type A, starting of matrix cracking is marked by green arrows, b) Sample of type B, long winded micro cracks are marked by red arrows.

Figure 10: SEM micrographs of carbonized samples: a) overview of a sample with surface treatment A, b) detailed picture of a single fiber of this sample type, c) overview of a sample with surface treatment B, showing the microcracks observed in the CT-study, d) detailed picture of a single fiber of this sample type. A distinct fiber-matrix debonding zone can be observed.

SEM pictures with higher magnification further reveal that the Cf-B fibers show a distinct partial debonding between single filaments and matrix after carbonization (Fig.10 (d)), in contrast to Cf-A fibers, which do not show such debonding (Fig.10 (a) and (b)). The debonding effect can be attributed to the volumetric shrinkage of the matrix resin (65 vol%) during carbonization. Due to the lower chemical functionality of the Cf-B surface, weaker fiber matrix adhesion can be expected in the CFRP state. Therefore, residual stress due to matrix shrinkage is relieved by partial fiber matrix debonding observed in Fig.10 (d). For CFRP samples consisting of Cf-A fibers, the higher surface functionality leads to a better bonding of fiber and matrix. Therefore, a stress release through the fiber matrix interface, as in samples of type B, is not possible and the interface stays intact. Fig.9 (a) suggests that in these samples, macroscopic stress is then relieved by matrix cracking, initiated at sample pores.

4.4 Micromechanical investigation of carbonized samples

In order to explore the effect of these two different types of interfaces on the mechanical behavior, single fiber push-in measurements were performed complemented by AFM. Fig.11 (a) shows the load-displacement curves for a set of push-in measurements. The load-displacement-curves for Cf-A fibers exhibit the same general shape as that of Cf-B fibers. At an indentation depth of 300 nm the load-displacement curves for both types of samples show a deviation from linear behavior. In contrast to Cf-B samples higher forces are observed throughout the indentation of Cf-A samples.

Figure 11: a) Set of push-in curves for each fiber type, b) selected exemplary curves with marked points for microscopic study.

In order to investigate the failure mechanism associated with the different load-displacement curves, several indents were stopped at distinct points of the respective load-displacement curves and analyzed microscopically by atomic force microscopy. The points chosen (A, B, C, D) for this investigation are marked on exemplary curves depicted in Fig.10 (b). Point A was chosen just before deviation of the linear elastic behavior occurs, i.e. at 250 nm for both samples. Point B was chosen in the nonlinear regime at 500 nm. Point C was chosen to be at 1000 nm, while point D signifies the end of the push-in measurement, chosen to be 1500 nm. Most Cf-A fibers show a load drop between points C and D, which signals fiber breakage. In Fig.12 we present the AFM images taken after unloading at points A, B, C and D. For Cf-A, first indication of plastic deformation of the fiber can be seen at point B (marked by red arrow). This plastic deformation increases at point C, while no residual displacement of the fiber relative to surrounding fibers or matrix can be observed. This observation suggests that the point of nonlinearity in the force-displacement curve has to be attributed to the limit of elasticity of the fiber under compression and does not indicate crack initiation. As described above, between point C and D fiber breakage occurs, which is confirmed by the corresponding AFM-image taken at point D. At this point, still no push-in of the fiber can be detected. In contrast, for Cf-B fibers, plastic deformation of the fibers is negligible. At point C a detectable residual displacement of the fiber is observed, indicating the beginning of a push-in. For the AFM-image at point D, push-in has advanced, with a fiber displacement of approximately 1 μm (off scale for chosen height-scale). In summary, a strong fiber-matrix adhesion can be deduced for Cf-A fibers, which prevents the observation of a fiber push-in. For Cf-B fibers the weaker fiber matrix bonding allows a conventional fiber push-in. Therefore, crack deflection at the fiber matrix interface can be expected to occur for this kind of composite. To verify this assumption, crack surfaces after three-point bending-tests were examined with SEM.

Figure 12: AFM-pictures of stopped indentations at significant points. Row on top: Points A-D for Cf-A fibers, row on the bottom: Points A-D for Cf-B fibers.

Figure 13: SEM micrographs of crack surfaces of carbonized samples. a) Cf-A, magnification 500, b) Cf-A, magnification 1000, c) Cf-B, magnification 500, d) Cf-B, magnification 1000.

The resulting SEM-pictures can be seen in Fig.13. The samples consisting of Cf-A fibers display plain crack surface (Fig.13 (a) and (b)), only interrupted by pores of mesoscopic size, signifying brittle fracture. Samples consisting of Cf-B fibers, on the other hand, display a rough surface, with fiber- and fiber bundle pull-out, indicating damage tolerant fracture behavior (Fig.13 (c) and (d)). Fig.14 shows SEM-pictures of single fibers at higher magnification. The fiber interface found at the crack surface is reminiscent of the fiber matrix interface on polished samples (Fig. 10), i.e. Cf-B samples show fiber matrix debonding, while Cf-A samples do not.

Figure 14: Detailed SEM pictures of single fibers found on the cracked surface. a) Cf-A, b) Cf-B.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The influence of fiber surface treatment on the fiber-matrix adhesion in carbon fiber reinforced carbon minicomposites was investigated. XPS-measurements were conducted to characterize the fiber surface, revealing differences in the concentration of oxygen functional groups on the respective surfaces. This difference in chemical composition of the fiber surface leads to very distinct differences in the microstructure of the respective CFRC material. For Cf-B fibers, with lower concentration of functional groups on the surface, fiber-matrix debonding occurs during pyrolysis and a characteristic debonding zone around single filaments develops. This is in contrast to Cf-A fibers, for which no debonding effects are observed. Finally, single fiber push-in measurements as well as fractographic investigations, suggest, that the fiber-matrix debonding in composites consisting of Cf-B fibers allow crack deflection and therefore exhibit damage tolerant behavior, while composites consisting of Cf-A fibers show brittle fracture behavior.

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